

TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI: ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI, TARAQQIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI

2025-yil 29-30-sentabr

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
SIRDARYO VILOYATI HOKIMLIGI
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YANGLING KASB-HUNAR VA TEXNIKA KOLLEJI**

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To‘plamga keltirilgan ma’ruza tezislarning mazmuni, undagi ma’lumotlar va me’yoriy hujjatlar hamda fikr-mulohazalar, takliflarning to‘g‘riligiga mualliflarning o‘zlari mas’uldirlar

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Furqatning

Ummati sargashtaman, yo Mustafo, aylang madad!

Tutmadim sunnat yo 'lin, ro'zi jazo aylang madad! (-B.30)

baytida Mustafo, ummat, sunnat, ro'zi jazo leksemalari badiiy matnda diniy mazmuni ifodalashga xizmat qilgan. Shuningdek, shoirning

Tavofi Ka'bag'a rahnamo bilan boramiz,

O'lumni chog'lab o'za qazo bilan boramiz. (-B. 73)

misrasi bilan boshlanuvchi g'azalida *Madina, Miyno, Safo, Marva, Imom Husayn, ka'ba, tavof, o'lum, qazo, haj, arkon, imom* singari o'ndan ortiq islom dini bilan bog'liq tushunchalarni ifoda etadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, badiiy tilni o'sha davr yoki umuman til taraqqiyoti tarkibidan ajratib olib bo'lmaydi. Zero, shoir hayotiy voqea-hodisalarni tasvirlab, obraz yaratar ekan, u so'zlashuv tili boyliklaridan, jonli tildagi sheva va kasb-hunarga oid til birliklaridan ham, adabiy til normalaridan ham keng foydalanadi. Furqat g'azallari ham adabiy-badiiy san'atlarga boyligi, o'zbek tili leksik imkoniyatlaridan samarali foydalanilganligi bilan ajralib turadi. Shoir g'azaliyotida badiiy tasvir vositalarini o'rinli va unumli qo'llashi natijasida lirik asar mazmuni va mohiyatini o'ziga xos tarzda ochib berishga erishgan.

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FROM QUANTITY TO AMBIGUITY: THE INDEFINITE USE OF NUMERALS IN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: Numerals represent a system of words denoting numbers that model reality in terms of quantity and are the main lexical means of expressing quantity in language. The concept of indefinite quantity also depends on the situation and context. This article examines the role of numerals in expressing ambiguity, focusing on comparative analysis of Azerbaijani and English.

Key words: vagueness, ambiguity, quantity, numeral, definiteness, indefiniteness, approximate quantity.

Numeral is the result of the projection of extranumerals in language, and the example of unity in a world of illusions and sets. Quantity is not only one of the forms of activity of numbers in matter, but also has a logical-philosophical nature and occupies a major place in the conceptual picture of the world. Numerals are ideas and forces with a symbolic meaning. Quantitative category is one of the important ontological categories that plays the role of methodological and worldview that has penetrated human existence, as well as mental event, the result of human perception of the quantitative definition of the real world and the classification activity of human thinking. This article deals of the numerals in indefinite meaning in Azerbaijani and English. Although the Azerbaijani language belongs to the Turkic language family and the English language belongs to the Indo-European language family we can find out similarities and differences by the help of comparative linguistics. First of all, it is worthwhile to note that, although quantifiers exist under different morphological distributions in two languages, they are integral parts in these languages. The quantifiers in Azerbaijani is studied under the numerals which is considered one of the main parts of speech, while in English they are included to the subgroups of the determinatives. As the category of quantity is a universal category in the languages, we cannot imagine the world languages without quantifying words.

The reasons for the usage of indefinite numerals in both languages can be divided into two groups: 1) objective reason, despite the lack of accurate/definite information; 2) subjective reason from the point of view of the choice of the speaker. In both languages universal features in the formation, development and evolution of numerals are observed. In compared languages, the same methods (counting and multiplication) are used in the formation of numerals. The history of numerals in both languages is ancient, and the main reason for their emergence is the need for people to count, numerate and name them. On the other hand, as the etymological basis of quantitative words, the parts of the human body - fingers, toes and others are performed.

Numeral is one of the main word groups in modern Azerbaijani linguistics. *"Today numeral is one of the main parts of speech that is included in the grammar of the Azerbaijani language and is thoroughly studied."*[1, p.172].

Quantifiers in English are semantically divided into universal and existential groups. Universal quantifiers express the amount and quantity of the entity in general, i.e. universal quantifiers mean everything. The English units */all, every, each/* belong to this type of quantifiers. Existential quantifiers express the existence of at least two things and objects, and words and expressions such as */some, any, several, many, much, a lot of, few, a few, little, a little/* belong to these quantifiers.

The expression of an approximate quantity in English is not limited to quantifiers. Although the role of quantifiers, indefinite quantitative indicators is undeniable, various words and phrases, even sentences, are used as auxiliary tools. A similar phenomenon exists in the Azerbaijani language. In addition to the indefinite numerals, words and expressions such as “*əksəriyyət*”, “*çoxluq*”, “*kifayət qədər*”, “*mümkün qədər*”, “*yaxın*”, “*qədər*”, “*təxminən*”, “*qeyri-dəqiq*”, “*hardasa (5 ədəd)*” are also used. When an indefinite quantitative category is presented as a functional-semantic field, its structure is divided into core and peripheral constituents [2, p.144.] Since the indefinite minority quantity belongs to the nuclear constituents, its expression carries the character of subjective assessment (emotive), the used vocabulary (lexemes) is adjusted to a neutral style. In the Azerbaijani language, the lexemes belonging to the nuclear field of indefinite quantity are: */az, azca, bir az, bir neçə, bir qədər/*, etc. In English, the lexemes like */little, few, some, scant, only, insufficient, short, meagre, insignificant, scarce, a bit of/* represent an indefinite quantity of minority.

According to the grammatical rules of the Azerbaijani language, nouns followed by the cardinal numerals and indefinite cardinal numerals cannot be used with plural suffix. However, it is possible to encounter plural nouns that are used before a cardinal numeral, in this case an indefinite majority or minority of a certain part is meant.

Nouns can be used in plural followed by indefinite numerals in some cases. R.Khalilov noted the following points in this regard: “1. *When the quantitative numeral is homogeneous; e.g.: İmtahanları dörd və beş qiymətlərlə başa çatdıraq.* 2. *The indefinite numeral has the approximate meaning, the parts of the whole are emphasized, a kind of figurative expression is created; e.g.: Bakı milyon işıqları ilə göz qurpırdı.* 3. *The indefinite numeral expresses an indefinite quantity and time concept; e.g.: Axşam saat doqquz radələrində məşğələmdən mənzilimə qayıdırdım. Balakəşi qırx yaşlarında olardı.*” [3, p.69].

In the Azerbaijani language, ordinal numerals accept the following nouns in singular, and in this case a concrete, definite quantitative concept is formed. However, in the Azerbaijani language, there are cases when nouns used after ordinal numerals are in the plural. Of course, in that case, it contains an indefinite quantity. R.Khalilov groups the cases of the nouns used with plural suffixes following ordinal numerals in the Azerbaijani language as follows: “1) while stating the parallel of time, object and event. For example, */Birinci günlər Yaqut qızdırma içində sayıqlayırdı/* (Ə. Məmmədخانlı). 2) when the ordinal numerals on the first side of the word combination are homogenous; For example, */Birinci, ikinci, üçüncü yerləri tutan komandalara rayon şurasının fəxri fərmanları verilmişdir/*” [3, p.70].

The use of fractional numerals in this sense in the language occurs in the combinations where decimal numerals are used. The richness of the language is evidenced by the fact that the fractional numerals have different shades of meaning out of their true meaning. In the example “*Fikirlərimin yüzə birini dinləyicilərə çatdırma bilmədim*” we cannot express definiteness.

The unparalleled role of the cardinal numeral */bir/* (*one*) in word creation also influenced the formation of indefinite quantifier word combinations. According to A. Demirchizade, , “*among the numerals, the numeral /bir/ is the unique which is used mostly in stylistic points and nuances*” in the Azerbaijani language [4, p.219]. */Bir/* - the cardinal numeral that does not indicate an exact quantity depends on the definite or indefinite context, the wishes and desires of the speaker, the accuracy or inaccuracy of the information, as well as the intonation. That is, accurate or inaccurate, complete or incomplete information can be transmitted to the listener depending on the context and situation. Of course, in this case, the meaning of the numeral */bir/* will be uncertain. When the numeral */bir/* is used with words such as */yığın, əmək, bölük, aləm, sürü, ovuc, topa, dəstə, anbar, dünya/* indefinite meaning of majority is formed. The numeral */bir/* is used together with the words */az, qədər, neçə, para/* to create the concept of minority: */bir az çörək, bir neçə sual, bir qədər su, bir para adam/*.

Definite numerals used with */çox/* take the ablative case suffix and form the indefiniteness of majority: */beşdən çox tələbə/, /ondan çox məqalə/,* etc. Although the starting point of the indefinite majority in these types of compounds is known, the exact quantitative range is uncertain.

By adding the endings */-ca, -cə, -la, -lə/* to the end of the cardinal numerals that have taken the plural suffix, majority expressing indefiniteness is created: */yüzlərcə məhkum, minlərlə tələbə, onlarla məktub/*. In Azerbaijani, we also encounter cardinal numerals with the suffixes */-dak, -dək, -cən, -cən/,* which undoubtedly means that in this case, cardinal numerals do not express a precise quantity, but an indefinite quantity. For example, we cannot make any assumptions about the precise quantity in combinations such as */minəcən tələbə/* or */yüzədək iştirakçı/*.

The words such as */yaxın, qədər, cən, dək, kimi/* are used with cardinal numerals and form indefinite quantity: */ona yaxın məktub, yüzəcən tələbə, minədək usta/*. Compounds that express uncertainty by using numerals that indicate different quantities side by side also express the concept of approximate quantity, depending on the context. */İştirakçılardan yalnız beş-altı nəfər təklif olunan layihə ilə maraqlandı//* or */Universitet tələbələrindən on-on beşi yarışda iştirak etməyə razılıq verdi//*.

Indefinite quantity can be expressed with some words denoting measure together with definite numerals. Although all words denoting measure do not create the idea of an indefinite quantity at first glance, when we go deeper into the matter, it is possible to find the concept of an indefinite quantity even in such combinations. For example, if we pay attention to the combinations */iki sətir yazı/* (two lines of writing) and */iki şələ odun/* (two bundles of firewood), at first glance, the combination */two lines of writing/* seems to be somewhat more specific than the other

combination. However, it should be taken into account that when we say */two lines of writing/*, we cannot determine exactly how many words are placed in each line. Of course, their quantity may vary depending on the number of letters in the words.

In English, although numerals are generally associated with precise quantities, they can also carry an indefinite meaning. They are used not to indicate an exact count, but to convey an impression of quantity. Phrases such as */a couple of, dozens of, or hundreds of/* rarely refer to their literal numerical value; instead, they serve to express “a few,” “many,” or “a large number,” respectively. Similarly, expressions like */one/* or */two/* may simply mean “some,” and */a hundred times/* is often employed to emphasize frequency rather than to provide a mathematical figure. This flexible use of numerals allows English to blur the line between precision and approximation, a phenomenon that finds parallels in many other languages, including Azerbaijani. In Azerbaijani, indefiniteness is primarily conveyed through indefinite numerals, whereas in English, it is expressed mostly using quantifiers. In both languages, indefiniteness signifies an imprecise or approximate quantity of the object being identified. Thus, numerals don't function only as denoting exact quantities, but also in the function of denoting indefiniteness, ambiguity, vagueness and approximation.

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OT LEKSEMALARINING BIRIKUVCHANLIK VA BIRIKTIRUVCHANLIK JIHLATLARI

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